

Research on the Working Group and Its Adjustment Mechanism for Serving Large Construction Projects

Zhongmei Li*

Shanghai University of Political Science and Law, Shanghai, China

*Author to whom correspondence should be addressed.

Abstract: *As a special working group with Chinese characteristics, it has the advantages of both matrix structure and temporary organization. It has the unique advantages of flat organizational structure, flexible and professional personnel, and efficient and orderly operation in the governance of non-routine affairs, which effectively makes up for the shortcomings of the traditional bureaucratic system. Different from the research on special working groups that focuses on the macro level, the special working groups operating at the grassroots level follow the logic of problem-solving and are buffers connecting the superior government and the grassroots society. Based on the establishment goals and survival cycle of the special working groups, this article divides the special working groups into four categories: emergency task attack type, routine task execution type, simple problem solving type, and complex problem adaptation type. The article takes the special working group serving the construction of Huawei's R&D center as a case study and delineates it as a complex problem adaptation type special working group. The adaptation mechanism of the special working group in the process of serving the construction of large-scale projects is studied. The study found that this type of special working group achieved cross-bureaucratic adaptation through resource calling mechanism, line communication mechanism, and joint consultation and linkage mechanism, effectively resolved many contradictions and conflicts in the process of project promotion, and laid the foundation for the orderly promotion of the project.*

Keywords: Special Working Group; Problem-Driven; Grassroots Governance; Non-Routine Affairs; Adjustment Mechanism.

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1. Problem Statement

The modernization of the grassroots governance system and capacity calls for high-level grassroots governance. In April 2021, the Central Committee issued the "Opinions of the CPC Central Committee and the State Council on Strengthening the Modernization of the Grassroots Governance System and Governance Capacity", pointing out that "grassroots governance is the cornerstone of national governance, and the coordinated promotion of township (street) and urban and rural community governance is a basic project for realizing the modernization of the national governance system and governance capacity". The "Decision of the CPC Central Committee on Further Comprehensively Deepening Reforms and Promoting Chinese-style Modernization" adopted at the Third Plenary Session of the 20th CPC Central Committee held in July 2024 further proposed: "Improve the social governance system. Adhere to and develop the 'Fengqiao Experience' in the new era, improve the urban and rural grassroots governance system led by the party organization that combines autonomy, rule of law, and moral governance, and improve the social governance system of co-construction, co-governance, and sharing". As the gathering point of population, material, information and other elements, the grassroots not only provides a spatial field for the spread and migration of various risks, but also has more obvious advantages in integrating resources and assisting governance.

At the same time, under the pressure of territorial responsibility, grassroots governments have assumed more diverse and complex governance tasks. Obviously, the existing bureaucratic management system is difficult to cope with unconventional governance tasks. With the continuous advancement of the modernization of national governance capabilities, grassroots governments and grassroots staff are facing more complex and changeable

affairs. The original bureaucratic system has increasingly become problematic, such as rigid organizational structure, poor communication between levels, and weak departmental coordination. Especially when encountering some unconventional affairs, the bureaucracy seems to be "incapable of doing it". Therefore, temporary task organizations such as working groups, leading groups, and political groups have become an organic supplement to the original organizations. Some scholars have distinguished working groups from other deliberative and coordinating institutions in terms of organizational functions, organizational structure, member determination, performance appraisal, and survival status, but the types of working groups themselves are not single.

Many scholars have studied task-driven special teams. Different from task-driven special teams, this article focuses on problem-solving-driven project-based special teams, which belong to the complex problem adaptation type in Table 1. The core issue is: how can the special teams formed at the grassroots effectively deal with the complicated governance problems and urgent governance needs? This article takes the construction of Huawei's R&D base in Jinze, Qingpu District, Shanghai as an example. The special team has made progress in exploration and achieved remarkable governance results, which has enabled Huawei projects to proceed smoothly. The special team uses problem-solving as the driving logic, people-first as the core value pursuit, and cross-mediation as the dispute resolution strategy. Through the cross-bureaucratic resource call mechanism, line communication mechanism, and joint consultation mechanism, it effectively coordinates contradictions, solves problems, and promotes the orderly progress of projects. It can become a model sample of special teams serving large-scale project construction and provide experience for special teams in large-scale project construction.

2. Literature Review

Leading groups, command centers, temporary organizations, and special working groups are increasingly becoming hot topics of research. This is the product of a series of problems, including the increasing complexity of grassroots governance affairs, increasing pressure on staff, the gradual rigidification of bureaucratic structures, and reduced efficiency. This type of organization is both a deliberately arranged Chinese style and a grassroots governance strategy that has emerged as a result.

2.1 Review of foreign literature

In the development process of organizational management, matrix organizational structure and temporary organization can be regarded as the important origin and first generation prototype of the working group to a certain extent. The cross-functional characteristics and multiple command line structure of the matrix organizational structure provide a key source of ideas for the resource integration and task orientation of the working group. Its horizontal communication mode that breaks down organizational barriers enables the resources of different departments to be efficiently converged and coordinated under a specific task framework. This advantage is reflected in the strong resource integration ability of the working group when dealing with complex tasks, and it can quickly gather the forces of all parties to invest in key tasks. The characteristics of temporary organizations being formed around specific complex tasks within a limited time and dynamically adjusting the structure according to the progress of the task are also inherited by the working group. When facing emergency tasks such as epidemic prevention and control and emergency response to emergencies, the working group can quickly form and flexibly adjust the personnel composition and work priorities to ensure the efficiency and pertinence of task execution. The working group has achieved further innovation and development on the basis of integrating the advantages of both.

In the field of organizational management, matrix structure organizations and temporary organizations are important research objects (Ford RC, Randolph WA, 1992; Lundin RA, Söderholm A, 1995). Matrix organizations adopt a cross-functional superposition model, build multiple command lines, and respond to time-limited tasks in the form of teams. They are both project-oriented and professional-oriented (Ford RC, Randolph WA, 1992). They originate from solving the information flow barriers of traditional bureaucratic organizations, breaking down barriers through horizontal communication, and adapting to complex dynamic environments. Although its dual management structure is conducive to resource allocation, it is easy to cause unclear definition of power and responsibility and management conflicts. Although it is effective in information and resource management, it has disadvantages such as high cost and high pressure. Temporary organizations are groups formed for specific complex tasks within a limited time. They are built around time, tasks, teams and transformations, and their structures change in stages with the progress of tasks (Packendorff J, 1995; Lundin RA, Söderholm A, 1995). At present, there is still room for expansion in research on team processes and task results. Compared with the other two, the working group has distinct Chinese characteristics. In terms of goal setting, the working group closely

focuses on core tasks such as national strategies, such as poverty alleviation and rapid response during epidemic prevention and control, and has a clear political orientation; matrix and temporary organizations mostly focus on internal or general complex tasks of the enterprise. In terms of resource integration, the working group can quickly gather resources from all parties with its administrative system and strong political mobilization; the matrix organization is restricted by the internal structure of the enterprise, and the temporary organization relies on the market and cooperative relations, and its resource allocation ability is relatively weak. At the decision-making and execution level, the working group is efficient and authoritative under the centralized and unified leadership; the matrix organization is prone to decision-making obstacles due to dual management (Ford RC, Randolph WA, 1992), and the temporary organization is affected by the temporary nature of members and the diversity of interests, and the decision-making cycle is relatively long. In view of the unique role of the working group in China's governance, in-depth exploration of its characteristics, mechanisms and laws is of far-reaching significance to national development.

Compared with the matrix organizational structure, the working group is more centralized and efficient in decision-making and execution mechanism. Due to the dual management structure of functional managers and project managers, the matrix organization is prone to power checks and balances and shirking of responsibilities in the decision-making process, resulting in low decision-making efficiency. Under the clear political orientation and centralized and unified leadership, the working group can make decisions quickly and execute them efficiently, avoiding the obstacles of internal management conflicts to the advancement of tasks. Compared with temporary organizations, the working group has unique advantages in resource acquisition. Temporary organizations rely on market mechanisms and cooperative relationships to obtain resources, and often face the problems of unstable resources and difficulty in allocation. Relying on a strong administrative system and political mobilization capabilities, the working group can gather rich and stable resources from all levels in a short period of time, effectively ensuring the smooth implementation of tasks. In terms of personnel composition and collaboration, the working group also combines and optimizes the strengths of both. Although matrix organizations and temporary organizations have achieved certain results in personnel collaboration, there are still problems such as high coordination costs and weak sense of belonging among members. The task force has built a close and efficient collaborative team by transferring key personnel across departments and levels, and dynamically absorbing various professional talents according to task requirements. In large-scale construction projects, the task force can accurately integrate professional talents in multiple fields such as planning, construction, and environmental protection to form a strong working force. At the same time, through clear division of responsibilities and efficient communication and coordination mechanisms, it ensures that team members have consistent goals and work together.

To sum up, while inheriting some characteristics of the matrix organizational structure and temporary organization, the working group has become a unique organizational form that adapts to China's governance needs through its own optimization and innovation. It plays an irreplaceable and key role in many fields such as national strategy implementation and social governance. Its integrated development model provides a valuable Chinese sample for organizational management theory and practice.

2.2 Domestic Literature Review

2.2.1 Differences from other temporary organizations

Liu Peng and Liu Zhipeng (2022) pointed out that the leading group is mainly responsible for decision-making and bears collective responsibility, while the working group focuses on policy implementation and individual responsibility. You Yu (2024) further explained that the organizational structure of the working group is more flexible and oriented towards project and issue resolution. It is significantly different from the leading group in terms of administrative resource consumption and the degree of member participation in implementation. For example, in the implementation of some local policies, the leading group is responsible for formulating policy directions, while the working group is responsible for the execution and supervision of specific implementation steps. The two are completely different in terms of work processes and responsibility definitions. Regarding the command center, Liu Ke and Xie Xinshui (2023) believe that its decision-making power is concentrated and responsibility is personalized in "urgent, difficult, dangerous, and heavy" tasks; the working group mainly performs special tasks and promotes work in a coordinated manner by integrating resources. For example, in natural disaster rescue scenarios, the command center quickly decides and deploys rescue strategies, and the working group is responsible for the specific deployment of rescue materials, resettlement of disaster victims, and other execution tasks. The division of labor between the two is clear, but the coordination and cooperation

mechanism needs to be studied in depth, especially in complex scenarios such as large-scale construction projects, where the responsibilities of various organizations at different stages overlap and change. Although existing research has clarified the differences between the working group and other organizations in terms of conventional functions, power structure, and architecture, there is insufficient research on the collaborative relationship and role transition of various organizations in complex project scenarios. For example, large-scale infrastructure construction projects involve multi-department and multi-stage tasks, and how different temporary organizations cooperate and when to change roles need to be explored in depth.

2.2.2 Definition analysis

Liu Peng and Liu Zhipeng (2024) defined the working group as a temporary organization that uses local bureaucratic resources and draws personnel to implement policies; Liu Ke and Xie Xinshui (2023) emphasized that it is a temporary organization that performs unconventional governance tasks and solves problems through cross-departmental cooperation; You Yu (2024) pointed out that it is an organization that integrates manpower, resources and authority to respond to temporary or urgent tasks. These definitions highlight the characteristics of the working group's temporary nature, task orientation, cross-departmental collaboration and reliance on bureaucratic resources. However, in the context of large-scale construction projects, the existing definition does not fully cover the formation, resource allocation and dynamic changes in the functions of the working group around the entire life cycle of the project. For example, in large-scale energy construction projects, the working group must not only coordinate all parties during the construction phase, but also consider the long-term impacts of energy delivery and ecological maintenance after the project is in operation. The current definition lacks in-depth elaboration on this.

2.2.3 Analysis of structure and functions

In terms of structure, Liu Ke and Xie Xinshui (2023) proposed that the working group is mostly flat, reducing hierarchical barriers, reducing supervision and coordination costs, enhancing organizational flexibility and mobility, and the personnel composition is cross-departmental and cross-level and dynamically adjusted, and the leadership is often concurrently held by the leaders of regular departments. Yang Liang (2022) demonstrated the model of the working group with unified power sources from the leading group and personnel transfer embedded in the regular organization through the case of D City, Y Province. In terms of functions, Liu Peng and Liu Zhipeng (2022) emphasized that the core function of the working group is policy implementation, and ensuring efficient implementation by clarifying responsibilities. You Yu (2024) found through research on the community comprehensive governance team that it not only performs tasks, but also coordinates resources and integrates the power of departments and blocks, effectively solving the drawbacks of bureaucratic governance. However, for the complex problem adjustment type working group in the scenario of large-scale construction projects, the structure and functions are unique. In terms of structure, the coordination of grassroots personnel from multiple departments requires the establishment of an efficient communication and coordination mechanism, the reasonable allocation of power and responsibility, and the optimization of personnel allocation according to the project stage. For example, in large-scale transportation hub construction projects, the requirements for engineering, safety, logistics and other personnel vary at different construction stages, and current research lacks targeted results. In terms of functions, in addition to routine tasks, it is also necessary to deal with complex issues derived from the project, such as dealing with relations with surrounding communities and ensuring long-term operational sustainability, etc. Existing research has not paid enough attention to this.

2.2.4 Exploration of operation mechanism

Li Ping and Yang Hongshan (2023) pointed out through their research on the Beijing Olympic "08 Environmental Office" that the working group relies on task-driven personnel transfer, responsibility-driven resource extraction, project-driven knowledge application and performance-driven evaluation incentive mechanism. For example, in the Olympic environmental governance, personnel from environmental protection, urban management and other departments were accurately transferred according to tasks; funds, equipment and other resources were obtained based on responsibility goals; members were encouraged to integrate multi-field knowledge innovation to solve problems; and performance standards were used to evaluate and reward members to stimulate their enthusiasm. Pang Guanglong (2024) found in the joint creation project of S Town, Hubei that the operation of the special team depends on authority transmission, organizational mobilization, information feedback and resource coordination mechanisms. Rely on the authority of leaders to ensure departmental cooperation; break through bureaucratic restrictions to allocate resources and integrate forces; adjust strategies through regular reporting; rely on high-level

leaders to integrate county-level resources. Li Zhen and Liu Yuling (2024) took the A City working group as an example and showed that its operation was affected by the level and task target field, and the functions, resource allocation and assessment mechanisms of special teams at different levels were different.

However, the research on the operation mechanism of complex problem adaptation teams around large-scale construction projects is still shallow. In large-scale construction projects, in addition to professional skills, the ability of personnel to deal with social problems and coordinate interests needs to be considered, because the project involves multiple interest groups, such as the resettlement of immigrants in the construction of large-scale water conservancy projects. The resource extraction mechanism should take into account the continuous supply of project operation service resources, such as the resource guarantee of public service facilities after the construction of urban new areas. The knowledge application mechanism should pay more attention to systematicness and comprehensiveness, and respond to multi-faceted challenges such as environmental, social, and economic challenges of the project, such as the balance of knowledge application between ecological protection and economic development. The evaluation and incentive mechanism needs to build a multi-dimensional long-term system, pay attention to long-term benefits and social impacts, such as considering the assessment of the long-term impact of large-scale industrial projects on local employment and the environment. At the same time, issues such as balancing departmental interests and powers in the transmission of authority, integrating grassroots innovation vitality in organizational mobilization, accurately capturing complex problems in information feedback, and efficiently utilizing resources throughout the life cycle in resource coordination all need to be further explored. These are crucial to the efficient operation of complex problem adaptation teams, and are related to the success or failure and sustainable development of large-scale construction projects and even national strategic construction projects. This article wants to start from the micro perspective, only from the type of "complex problem adaptation work team", taking the Huawei center work team as an example, and deeply analyze the operation mechanism of this type of work team. The functions and operation mechanisms of the project-based work team are also different from the series of operation methods proposed by existing research. It is neither like the headquarters and the leading group that only focus on "resolution" functions such as planning, command, and control, nor is it one of the four functional divisions of decision-making, coordination, supervision, and execution proposed by Li Zhen and Liu Yuling (2024). It is a complex of multiple functions of "planning + resolution + coordination + execution + service", a buffer between the superior administrative organization and the grassroots organization, taking on tasks from above and serving the masses below.

3. Classification of special working groups

In addition to being different from other deliberative and coordinating institutions, the working groups themselves are also diverse. Liu Peng and Liu Zhipeng (2024) divided the working groups into four categories based on the purpose of establishment and operation mechanism: strong disposal type, task-breaking type, coordination and statement type, and gap-filling type. The strong disposal type is mainly used to deal with emergencies and adopts a substantive operation mode; the task-breaking type is aimed at normal government work and has clear task goals and quantitative standards; the coordination and statement type mainly undertakes information coordination and institutional liaison functions and is difficult to operate in a substantive manner; the gap-filling type is mainly to fill the gaps in the government's daily work field, mostly focusing on conveying the spirit of superiors and internal reform. Liu Ke and Xie Xinshui (2023) divided the working groups into "deliberative and coordination type", "command and supervision type" and "special execution type" from the perspective of duty performance. However, they pointed out that the first two categories are sometimes called "working groups", more because of the popularization of the concept of working groups. In the strict sense, working groups should be mainly responsible for executing unconventional temporary tasks. Li Ping [3](2023) believes that task-driven is the starting point of the special working group. Therefore, she distinguished four types of special working group operations based on the different task attributes and member boundaries: project cooperation, platform sharing, personnel transfer, and department integration. Li Zhen and Liu Yuling [4](2024) made a detailed sub-type division of the special working group from the perspective of functional positioning and structural type. The functional positioning is subdivided into decision-making supervision type, supervision execution type, decision-making coordination type, and coordination execution type. The structural type is subdivided into loose type, tight type, and mixed type. The former directly defines the special working group as task-driven and thus ignores the problem-solving driven special working group. Although the latter subdivided the sub-types of the special working group, it ignored the differences in the goals and survival cycles of the special working group due to its excessive focus on the functional structure after the establishment of the special working group.

The current classification method of scholars provides a clear framework for understanding the functions and

operation modes of working groups in different situations. However, the existing classification is mostly based on macro-task types and general functions of organizations. The working groups around large-scale construction projects, especially those that solve a series of complex problems brought about by the projects and transform into normalized service-oriented organizations after the projects are implemented, have not been fully reflected in the existing classification system. During the implementation of the project, such working groups need to coordinate grassroots staff from multiple functional departments to deal with complex problems caused by the project, such as the environment, society, and economy. Their unique operation mode and development path are worth exploring.

Therefore, scholars often assume that the goal of establishing a special working group is to complete a specific task, thus ignoring the problem-solving type of special working group, and tend to analyze it from the organizational structure and organizational function of the special working group entity. Indeed, the goal of establishing a special working group is also very important, which fully reflects that the dominant forces within the special working group are different. Task-driven types are often led by superiors, and subordinates only passively cooperate, while problem-solving types are often established by superiors and only become the basis of legitimacy or have symbolic significance. Subordinates are the dominant force and take the initiative to solve problems. Although they are all temporary organizations, their organizational survival cycles are different, which means that the complexity of the functions they undertake is different. A special working group with a shorter duration often means that the special working group performs a single type of function and the problems to be solved are simple. Generally, it only undertakes the functions of supervision and execution; while a special working group with a longer duration often undertakes multiple functions and solves more complex problems. Therefore, this article will divide the working group into task-driven and problem-solving driven types according to the establishment goals, and then divide it into temporary and continuous types according to the life cycle of the working group. Combining the two, they can be summarized into the four types in Table 1.

Table 1: Four types of working groups (Source: author’s own)

Special class life cycle Special class set goals	Mission-driven (Superior organization + subordinate cooperation)	Problem Solving (Superior leadership + subordinate leadership)
Short-term (End of task/question)	Emergency mission attack (Emergency Task Force for COVID-19)	Simple problem solving (Community Renovation Working Group)
Persistent transformation (From temporary to permanent)	Regular task execution (Special Task Force for Eliminating Organized Crime and Evil)	Complex problem adaptation (Huawei R&D Center Special Team)

Emergency task-based task force: A task force that quickly convenes subordinates to cooperate in solving a major emergency problem that has attracted the attention of superiors, concentrates on overcoming urgent and significant tasks in a short period of time, and disbands as the crisis is resolved. This type of task force is characterized by emergency response, great impact, and short duration. For example, in the early stages of a major public health emergency such as the COVID-19 outbreak, local governments quickly formed emergency task forces for epidemic prevention and control in order to quickly control the spread of the epidemic. The task force members include personnel from multiple departments such as health, transportation, and public security. They work together to organize large-scale nucleic acid testing, allocate medical supplies, and control the flow of personnel. When the epidemic is initially controlled and related work is transferred to normalized management, the emergency task force will complete its mission and disband. Cheng Youquan, deputy director of the Supervision Bureau of the National Health Commission, introduced at the meeting: Each provincial joint prevention and control mechanism will set up a provincial special team to rectify the problem of "layer by layer adding" in accordance with the special team structure of the comprehensive group of the joint prevention and control mechanism of the State Council, strengthen organizational leadership, clearly specify the provincial leaders in charge of epidemic prevention and control as conveners of the special team, draw on capable personnel to form a special team, conscientiously perform their duties, ensure the efficient operation of the special team, and promptly correct and resolve problems reported by the masses.[5]

Regular task execution type special team: a special team formed to complete a complex task assigned by the superior, and due to the complexity of the task, it was transformed from a temporary organization to a permanent

organization. This type of special team presents the characteristics of difficult tasks, high pressure, and bureaucracy. For example, the special team for poverty alleviation and the special team for cracking down on gangsters and eliminating evil. In the process of implementing the poverty alleviation strategy, governments at all levels have set up special teams for poverty alleviation. The members of the special team include staff from multiple departments such as the Poverty Alleviation Office, the Agriculture and Rural Bureau, the Water Conservancy Bureau, the Education Bureau, the Housing and Construction Bureau, and the Human Resources and Social Security Bureau. They are responsible for formulating and implementing the poverty alleviation plan for the local area, accurately identifying the poor, implementing a series of measures such as industrial poverty alleviation, education poverty alleviation, health poverty alleviation, and relocation poverty alleviation, continuously tracking and evaluating the poverty alleviation effect, and adjusting the poverty alleviation strategy according to the actual situation. Poverty alleviation is a long-term and arduous task. After years of hard work and achieving a comprehensive victory, related work continues to be promoted in the form of rural revitalization. The functions of some special teams for poverty alleviation have also been transformed or integrated into the new rural revitalization work system, becoming a permanent organizational force serving rural development. [6] In April 2020, the National Anti-gang Office set up a special working group and organized a working mechanism of "five-level secretaries taking the lead and dual special teams of discipline inspection and public security". From the central government to the local governments, "campaign-style governance" was adopted to temporarily station at the local level. As the special campaign against gangs and evil forces is coming to an end, the central government requires that the special struggle against gangs and evil forces be normalized, and the special working group against gangs and evil forces will also be transitioned to a permanent institution. In 2021, the General Office of the CPC Central Committee and the General Office of the State Council issued the "Opinions on Regularly Carrying out the Struggle against Gangs and Evil Forces to Consolidate the Results of the Special Struggle", which clearly proposed to improve the leadership organization, conduct regular research and deployment, strengthen comprehensive guarantees, strengthen professional teams, and strengthen positive publicity. Clearly referring to the composition and division of labor of the original National Anti-gang and Evil Forces Special Struggle Leading Group, the central government established the National Anti-gang and Evil Forces Leading Group and its office, and party committees and relevant departments at all levels retained corresponding leadership and service agencies to achieve normal operation.[7]

Simple problem-solving type, a temporary organization organized to solve a special problem in the area, and a working group that is disbanded as the problem is solved. This type of working group is characterized by large number, regionality, and short duration. Its task focuses on solving a local problem. Once the problem is solved, the special group will be disbanded. For example, when an old community is undergoing renovation, in order to solve problems such as aging pipelines, insufficient parking spaces, and messy greening in the community, the local street or community will set up a special team for the renovation of old communities. The members of the special team include community staff, construction party representatives, and residents' representatives. They jointly negotiate to solve problems in the renovation process, such as determining pipeline renovation plans, rationally planning parking spaces, and optimizing greening layouts. When the community renovation is completed, the work of the special team is over. For example, Nanjing Gulou: The installation of elevators in old communities has started "acceleration". The special team members are composed of street community staff, elevator installation company technicians, planning and housing construction department staff, and residents' representatives. They are responsible for coordinating residents' opinions, handling planning approval procedures, supervising the quality of elevator installation, and resolving conflicts and disputes during construction. When the work of installing the elevator in the community is completed and residents can use the elevator normally, the working group will be disbanded and the subsequent maintenance of the elevator will be the responsibility of the relevant property and professional maintenance company.[8]

Complex problem adaptation type: Under the leadership of the superior, a special working group composed of grassroots staff from multiple functional departments to solve a series of complex problems brought about by a certain project, which is transformed into a normalized service-oriented organization as the project is implemented. This type of working group presents complex and adaptive characteristics. For example, a special working group for the construction of a large industrial park. When building a large industrial park, a series of complex issues such as land acquisition, planning approval, infrastructure construction, and investment attraction will be involved. The superior department takes the lead and organizes grassroots staff from multiple functional departments such as land, planning, construction, and investment attraction to form a special working group. During the construction of the industrial park, the special team constantly coordinates the relationship between all parties and solves various problems encountered. When the industrial park is completed, some of the personnel in the special team may be transformed into service personnel for the operation and management of the park, and continue to provide services

for the entry, operation and development of enterprises in the park. The Huawei R&D Center working group studied in this paper is a complex problem adaptation type. It aims to serve the construction of Huawei R&D Center. It has established a temporary party branch with 8 working groups. Its main tasks include coordinating population management, safety supervision, traffic organization, community services and other work in the construction of major projects. In January 2022, three members of the Xicen Community Party Committee were included in the special group, and it was renamed the Community Management Working Group. It implemented a team with two signs and centralized office. It has a community party committee, a community committee and four professional committees, including community party building services, affairs acceptance, conflict mediation, community management, health services and other functional departments. By March 2023, with the gradual advancement of Huawei's construction site, the working group's functions were gradually transformed, and it was renamed the Xicen Community Management Center and became a permanent institution.

This type of work team, which focuses on large-scale construction projects, solves complex problems and transforms into a normalized service-oriented organization, has significant characteristics of complexity and adaptability. The complexity is reflected in the fact that its personnel composition includes grassroots staff from multiple functional departments. These personnel have different professional backgrounds and work experience, and need to work together in the team to jointly deal with the multiple and complex problems involved in the project. For example, in a large-scale infrastructure construction project, the team may bring together grassroots personnel from multiple departments such as planning, construction, environmental protection, and transportation. It must not only ensure the smooth progress of the project, but also deal with social conflicts caused by land acquisition and environmental impacts during construction. This requires team members to have cross-domain knowledge and collaboration capabilities. Adaptability is reflected in the fact that it constantly adjusts its operating methods and functional positioning as the project progresses. In the project preparation stage, the focus of the team's work is to coordinate resources from all parties, formulate project plans, and solve problems such as pre-procedure handling; in the project construction stage, the focus of work shifts to on-site construction management, quality supervision, and communication and coordination with surrounding communities; and after the project is implemented, the team needs to transform into a normalized service-oriented organization, responsible for the subsequent maintenance and operation management of the project, and tracking and evaluating the long-term social and economic impact of the project. This dynamic adaptation process is a key link that is rarely addressed in the existing work team classification.

From the perspective of practical impact, such working groups are of great significance to the construction of national strategies. Large-scale construction projects are often important carriers for the implementation of national strategies, such as the construction of major national transportation hubs and the development of energy projects. The effective operation of working groups is directly related to whether the projects can be completed on time and with high quality, which in turn affects the realization of national strategic goals. Taking the construction projects of major national energy bases as an example, the working groups must not only coordinate and solve the technical difficulties and funding issues in the project construction, but also deal with the social problems such as the ecological environment and resettlement of immigrants that may be brought about by the projects. By integrating grassroots forces and timely adjusting work strategies, such working groups can ensure the smooth progress of the projects and achieve sustainable development after the projects are implemented, providing strong support for the long-term and stable implementation of national energy strategies. However, there is a relative lack of research on such working groups in the academic community, and there is a lack of in-depth discussions on their formation principles, operating mechanisms, transformation strategies, and performance evaluation. This not only limits our comprehensive understanding of the organizational form of working groups, but also is not conducive to better playing the role of such working groups in the construction of national strategies in practice. Therefore, in-depth research on complex problem-adaptive working groups to fill this research gap is of great theoretical and practical significance.

4. Analysis Structure and Case Studies

4.1 Analysis structure: structure-process

The structural-process analysis paradigm proposed by Wu Xiaolin is an important development of structural functionalism. Structural functionalism lacks temporal and dynamic research, while structural-process theory connects the macro and micro, returns to middle-level theory, and integrates action and structure. [9]In grassroots social governance, project work teams are formed under the pressure of territorial and bureaucratic pressures. The structure gives them power, and various subjects interact around power and resource games. The process is the

link between action and structure. When the work team is in operation, horizontal departments and vertical levels share information, resources, and communicate and collaborate, reflecting "adaptation" and "breaking", breaking the binary opposition. Structure and process are interdependent. In the process of promoting the project, the organizational structure of the team is shaped by the structure and continuously improved due to process changes. This paradigm tells us that we should attach importance to the coordination of the two in various fields to achieve effective docking and benign interaction between the macro and micro.

Figure 1: The working group's operating mechanism in terms of structure and process

The figure shows the operating mechanism of a working group in terms of structure and process. From the structural perspective, local responsibility, institutional environment and bureaucratic system play a decisive role in the working group. They assign tasks and provide resources, which reflects the setting of the action framework by the structure. The working group itself has a certain organizational structure, which is given by the structure. From the process perspective, there are two dimensions in the operation of the working group: horizontal and vertical. Horizontally, it is cross-departmental collaboration and consultation, and vertically, it is cross-bureaucratic resource allocation. The two together form a cooperative network, enabling the working group to form a joint force. In this process, the working group promotes the project by decomposing tasks and protects people's livelihood by solving problems, which reflects the "adaptation" and "break" of the process to the structure.

In general, the working group operation mechanism shown in the figure well reflects the structure-process analysis paradigm. The structure provides the foundation and framework for the working group, while the process is the dynamic practice of the working group to achieve the goal of protecting people's livelihood and promoting project goals. The two are interdependent and influence each other. While providing guarantees, the structure also restricts the process, and the process continuously promotes the optimization and improvement of the structure in adaptation and disruption.

4.2 Case introduction: Special working group serving large-scale construction projects

4.2.1 Background of establishment

As a key project of the Yangtze River Delta Integration Demonstration Zone, the "Huawei Qingpu R&D Center" is located in Xicen Community, Jinze Town, Qingpu District. It is an important carrier for Shanghai to implement the national strategy of Yangtze River Delta integration and build a science and technology innovation center with global influence. It is also a key node of the Yangtze River Delta digital trunk line. The project is huge in size and faces difficulties in safe construction such as complex and diverse types, concentrated contradictions, and superimposed social risks. First, the population is rapidly introduced. The actual population in the area under the jurisdiction of the local Jinze Police Station is about 46,000 (about 18,000 permanent residents), and there are about 16,000 workers on the construction site of the Huawei project. After completion, the actual population stock in the area is about 30,000. Second, the management difficulty has increased. The project has established eight groups, and the eight groups started construction simultaneously. The coordination during the construction process is difficult, and the management, operation and scheduling requirements are high. Third, multiple points are blooming in the surrounding areas. More than a dozen projects are under construction in and around Xicen,

including the Xicen Science and Technology Innovation Park, Shanghai-Suzhou-Lake High-speed Railway, the western extension of Line 17, and the second phase of resettlement housing. Major projects such as the Yuandang shoreline restoration and the waterside living room are accelerating, and various risk factors continue to be complex and intertwined. In order to solve the practical problems of safe construction of major projects, the Jinze Town Party Committee and government attach great importance to it, take the initiative to take action, set up a special working group in Xicen Community, and strive to create a demonstration model of safe construction of super-large construction sites to promote the smooth implementation of national strategies.

4.2.2 Organizational structure

The working group is led by the town government. The secretary and mayor of Jinze Town serve as the commander and deputy commander respectively. A "special group" organizational structure working model under the leadership of the Party Committee is established. 28 elite soldiers are selected from 17 relevant functional departments to form the Xicen Community Social Management Special Group. The members are double-sided assessed by their original units and the working group, and they work part-time. A temporary party branch is established with 8 working groups. The main tasks include coordinating population management, safety supervision, traffic organization, community services and other work in the construction of major projects. There are also three auxiliary forces: 36 social security team members of the Xicen Police Station, 25 grid team members, and 9 city appearance management team members. In January 2022, three members of the Xicen Community Party Committee will be included in the special group, renamed the Community Management Working Group, and a team and two signs will be centralized and co-located. It will have a community party committee, a community committee and four professional committees, including community party building services, affairs acceptance, conflict mediation, community management, health services and other functional departments. By March 2023, as Huawei's construction site gradually progressed, the functions of the working group were gradually transformed and renamed the Xicen Community Management Center, becoming a permanent institution. The functional departments were also adjusted accordingly, and the personnel structure continued the special team model, but personnel could also be promoted through rotation training in the special team.

Figure 2: Organizational structure of functional departments of the working group

4.2.3 Responsibilities of the special team

First, in terms of project security. First of all, it is related coordination work, coordinating the parking issues of Huawei project group buses and sewage pipes, coordinating various functional departments to speed up the sewage

network connection project, calling on sewage treatment plants to investigate and dredge pipes several times, and prohibiting Huawei's general contractor from discharging sewage into the river. Secondly, site safety supervision, adopting a combination of "regular inspection + irregular spot checks", inspecting and supervising the construction sites, shops along the street, homestays, small restaurants, villages, public safety and micro-firefighting, and other production, fire and food safety, urging enterprises to do a good job in hidden danger investigation, rectification, make-up classes and review work. 1,231 various hidden dangers were found, and a total of 1,226 were rectified. A total of eight on-site inspection records were issued, ordering rectification orders within a time limit, and inquiry notices. Fire protection publicity month and safety production month theme activities were actively carried out. Through the construction of friendship talks with the construction site group, various safety publicity materials and posters were distributed, and the "first lesson of construction" classroom was used to enhance the safety awareness of migrant workers. Finally, in terms of law enforcement support, the task force and Jinze Police Station insisted on cracking down on all kinds of illegal and criminal activities, effectively maintaining the stability of public security in the task force area, ensuring the normal construction of enterprises, and adhering to the management concept of prevention first, especially the implementation of five management mechanisms such as pre-management, anti-check management, and hierarchical management in the Huawei area. A total of 1,035 hierarchical WeChat groups were created to publicize various fraud safety warning education through the hierarchical management mechanism. With 100,000 personnel flow in the Huawei area throughout the year, only one fraud case occurred. Through pre-management, a total of 734 people on the red list and 321 people on the yellow list were sorted out, especially during the epidemic. A large number of problematic personnel were cleared. Effectively support the relevant work of various groups such as population management conflicts, mediation, safety, supervision projects, and services, and successfully handle more than 70 group gathering rights protection incidents.

Second, in terms of population services. First of all, in terms of community management, a cleaning plan for the construction roads of Huawei's construction sites was formulated. Through cleaning work. Yang Chen and road pollution around Huawei's construction sites have been effectively improved. For the garbage classification related work of Huawei's group canteen, spot checks are carried out from time to time, and four garbage classification penalties are imposed to deal with 38 dust. The special class jointly with the police station comprehensive law enforcement team market station Chengyun handled the rectification of the district gathering stalls and migrant workers, and arranged personnel to be stationed in key areas. Secondly, population management, the "six ones, eight musts" construction site population service management model is implemented, the population labeling management is strengthened, and the accuracy of the actual population registration is fully improved. The Huawei Qingpu R&D Center project site actual population service management station is established, and a stationmaster is stationed. Each of the eight construction groups has an actual population information collection room, and 16 community comprehensive coordinators are stationed to be responsible for the target management tasks of the construction site. The town population office and the special class population group organize the coordinators to carry out self-inspection of the actual population information quality twice a week. And the most important work of conflict coordination and resolution, using proactive, patient, caring, and follow-up supervision methods to properly resolve all kinds of conflicts and disputes. During the lockdown period, through the "sinking" dispute mediation mechanism, we actively surveyed and checked all kinds of unstable situations, and at the same time publicized various labor laws and regulations, giving full play to the role of people's mediation as the "first line of defense", and resolved multiple collective wage-demanding incidents. At the special node of the 20th National Congress, we started the "5+2, day and night" work mode, overcame all difficulties at home, took the initiative to go deep into the front line of the construction site, and safeguarded the legitimate rights and interests of workers. Timely mediation and handling of collective incidents such as the accidental death of workers during the 20th National Congress, family members gathered to ask for compensation, and more than 60 members of the dismissed team demanded an increase in various types of compensation, making positive contributions to the smooth convening of the 20th National Congress. Since the establishment of the special team, a total of 71 disputes involving construction sites, enterprises, villages, etc. have been resolved, involving 2,287 people and an amount of more than 26.77 million yuan, and 111 people's mediation agreements have been prepared.

Finally, the comprehensive coordination aspect. The comprehensive coordination group is responsible for the daily work of the special team. Through the working mode of daily dynamics, weekly reports and monthly summaries, it sorts out key tasks and summarizes work experience, analyzes the causes of problems and puts forward rectification suggestions. Since the establishment of the special team, the comprehensive coordination group has organized 51 liaison meetings, 111 field visits, compiled 127 special edition daily dynamics, 23 special team weekly reports, organized seven flood prevention and typhoon prevention inspections, and inspected and guided the safe evacuation of more than 10,000 people from various groups.

5. Operational Logic (Bureau-level Tasks + Grassroots Services)

5.1 Problem Solving: The Driving Logic of the Task Force

5.1.1 People first: the core value and orientation of the working group

In the operation system of the working group serving large-scale construction projects, the concept of people-first constitutes the core and action orientation of its value system. Large-scale construction projects have a wide range of social impacts and involve the vital interests of many people. The working group deeply understands the fundamental position of the interests of the people in the entire life cycle of the project. From the initial planning and specific implementation of the project to the subsequent operation and maintenance management, the needs, expectations and rights of the people are taken into consideration. For example, in the project site selection and planning and design stage, the working group actively practices the principle of public participation, and through organizing hearings, in-depth community visits and surveys, etc., it widely collects opinions and suggestions from surrounding residents to ensure that the layout and design of the project meet the expectations of the people for living environment, traffic convenience, etc., and avoids negative impacts on residents' lives. In the process of project promotion, in response to environmental problems such as noise and dust that may be generated by construction, the special team adheres to the strategy of prevention first, formulates scientific and reasonable response plans in advance, and strives to minimize the interference with people's daily lives, thereby demonstrating respect and protection for the quality of life of the people. This people-centered value orientation not only effectively protects the basic rights and interests of the people, but also builds a solid bridge of trust between the people and the project, creates a good social atmosphere for the smooth implementation of the project, and lays a broad mass foundation.

5.1.2 Pre-intervention mediation: proactive intervention and conflict resolution strategies by the working group

Faced with the complex and diverse interest patterns and potential conflicts in large-scale construction projects, the working group took forward mediation as an action strategy and demonstrated a proactive working attitude. The implementation of large-scale construction projects usually involves a series of key links that are very likely to cause interest disputes, such as land acquisition, house demolition, and construction disturbances. If they are not handled in a timely and proper manner, it is very likely to lead to the intensification and escalation of conflicts, which will in turn pose a serious threat to the project progress and social stability. The members of the working group took the initiative to go deep into the grassroots, intervene in the key nodes that may breed problems in advance, and actively carry out in-depth and detailed communication and coordination with all relevant stakeholders. Taking land acquisition as an example, the members of the working group had in-depth face-to-face exchanges with the farmers whose land was acquired, patiently explained the land acquisition policies and regulations and compensation standards, and listened carefully to the farmers' demands and concerns. For the reasonable demands raised by the farmers, they were promptly fed back to the higher authorities and coordinated with the relevant departments to properly resolve them; for unreasonable demands, they adhered to the principles of objectivity and fairness, explained and dredge them with a sincere and pragmatic attitude, and effectively avoided further deterioration of the contradictions. Through this forward-looking and proactive mediation method, the working group resolved many potential conflicts in the bud, created a harmonious and stable external environment for project construction, effectively ensured that the project could proceed smoothly according to the established plan, and at the same time maintained the overall harmony and stability of society.

5.1.3 Problem Solving: The Nature of the Working Group's Organizational Behavior and the Path to Achieving its Goals

Solving problems constitutes the essential meaning of the existence of the working group and the core embodiment of organizational behavior. Focusing on the task objectives of large-scale construction projects, the working group quickly responds to and formulates practical solutions to various governance problems encountered during the implementation of the project. Whether it is a technical bottleneck, a shortage of funds or a coordination dilemma, the working group actively integrates the resources of multiple subjects and mobilizes the forces of all parties to respond in a coordinated manner. For example, when the project construction encounters technical difficulties, the working group quickly forms a technical research team composed of experts in related fields to jointly conduct in-depth research and explore solutions; in the face of funding shortages, actively coordinate with financial

departments, financial institutions, etc., to ensure sufficient funds for the project by seeking financial support and expanding financing channels; in terms of coordinating relations between all parties, give full play to the role of bridge and link, and promote close cooperation and coordination between different departments and different stakeholders. Through this proactive organizational behavior model of problem-solving, the working group ensures that large-scale construction projects can overcome numerous difficulties, smoothly achieve expected goals, and contribute to local economic development and social progress.

5.2 Crossing bureaucratic levels: the operating mechanism of the working group

5.2.1 Party building leadership: integration and deployment mechanism of human and financial resources

Party building plays a fundamental leading role in the operation of the special working group, especially in the integration and allocation of human and financial resources. The party organization has strong cohesion and appeal in the special working group. By giving full play to the leading function of party building, it can efficiently integrate the forces of all parties and ensure that human and financial resources converge on large-scale construction projects. At the level of manpower deployment, the party organization, relying on its organizational advantages, selects and transfers party members and cadres with strong political literacy and superb business capabilities from different departments and levels to enrich the special working group and build a professional, experienced and strong working team. Under the unified leadership of the party organization, these party members and cadres can quickly clarify their respective responsibilities and form a collaborative and efficient working force to provide solid human support for the project promotion. In terms of the allocation of financial resources, the party organization can raise sufficient funds for the project through diversified means such as coordinating with the financial department, seeking financial support from higher authorities, and guiding social capital participation. For example, the government can be encouraged to introduce special financial support policies to give priority to the funding needs of large-scale construction projects; actively carry out investment promotion activities to attract enterprises to participate in project investment and construction, and broaden the source of funds. With the help of the human and financial resources integration and allocation mechanism under the leadership of Party building, the working group can provide strong resource guarantees for the smooth implementation of large-scale construction projects.

5.2.2 Linkage between top and bottom: Optimization mode of hierarchical collaboration and task execution

The working group follows the coordination mechanism of linkage between the upper and lower levels in the process of operation, realizing the organic combination and complementary advantages of superior leadership and subordinate leadership. The superior department plays a key role in leadership and guidance in the working group system, providing macro-policy guidance for the project, clarifying the work direction and goals, and supervising and evaluating the overall promotion of the project. The superior leaders ensure that the work of the working group is highly consistent with the overall strategy of local economic and social development by formulating strategic plans and issuing task indicators. At the same time, the superior department provides strong support for the working group to solve cross-departmental and cross-regional problems encountered in the process of project promotion with its resource integration and coordination capabilities. However, in the specific project implementation link, the subordinate department is in a dominant position and is responsible for the daily management and actual operation of the project. The subordinate leadership is reflected in the working group formulating detailed work plans and implementation plans based on the actual situation of the project, organizing and implementing various tasks of project construction, and promptly feedback project progress and problems to the superior. This linkage mechanism between the upper and lower levels not only ensures that the project follows the policy orientation and development strategy at the macro level, but also gives full play to the subjective initiative and flexibility of the subordinate departments in actual operations, so that the working group can effectively deal with various specific problems in project implementation and ensure the smooth progress of the project.

5.2.3 Local collaboration: strategies for the reorganization and coordinated use of local resources

Local coordination constitutes an important part of the working group's operation mechanism, and its core lies in the in-depth reorganization and coordinated use of various resources in the project location. The areas where large-scale construction projects are located are rich in natural, social and cultural resources, but these resources are often scattered in the hands of different entities, lacking an effective integration and coordinated utilization mechanism. Through the local coordination mechanism, the working group breaks the fragmentation between

resources, organically integrates the scattered resources, and realizes the optimal allocation and efficient use of resources. For example, during the project construction process, the working group can coordinate multiple entities such as local governments, enterprises, and social organizations to participate in project construction and operation. The local government can provide support in terms of land and policies; enterprises participate in project investment and construction with their technical, financial and management advantages; social organizations play an active role in community mobilization and public opinion collection. In addition, the working group focuses on exploring and utilizing local cultural resources, integrating cultural elements into project construction, and enhancing the cultural connotation and social value of the project. Through the local coordination mechanism, the working group can fully mobilize various resources in the project location, form a good situation of co-construction and sharing, provide all-round support for the successful implementation of large-scale construction projects, and promote the coordinated development of local economy and society.

6. Summary and Outlook

Through an in-depth analysis of the special working groups serving large-scale construction projects and their adaptation mechanisms, this article comprehensively reveals the operating mechanisms, challenges and coping strategies of such special working groups in the context of grassroots governance, and provides corresponding theoretical interpretation and practical guidance for the practice of special working groups in large-scale project construction.

From the perspective of the operating mechanism, the task force, under the driving logic of problem solving, has always adhered to the concept of people first, fully considered the interests of the people at all stages of the project, and demonstrated a strong value orientation; the institutional pressure of maintaining order ensures the standardization and stability of the work, and provides an institutional framework for the operation of the task force; and the organizational behavior of problem solving highlights its pragmatic and efficient work style. In the cross-bureaucratic operating mechanism, the resource call at the town level, the bottom-up line communication, and the horizontal multi-department consultation and linkage have effectively integrated the resources of all parties, broken the shackles of the traditional bureaucratic system, and improved work efficiency and problem-solving capabilities.

In terms of bureaucratic tasks, the Party building leadership has injected strong ideological cohesion and organizational support into the special team, ensuring the correctness of the work direction; the personnel allocation model of elite soldiers and strong generals reflects the combination of flexibility and professionalism, meeting the multi-faceted needs of the project; resource allocation has enhanced the resource base of the special team from both internal optimization and external expansion, providing a solid backing for the project advancement. However, the special team also faces challenges such as complex service fields and delayed organizational coordination during operation. In this regard, the special team relies on rich experience to deal with complex problems, and localized personnel play the advantage of "close distance" communication to resolve conflicts. At the same time, by building a sound communication and coordination mechanism, the efficiency of organizational coordination is improved.

Looking ahead, with the continuous advancement of the modernization of the social governance system and governance capacity, the role of the working group in the construction of large-scale projects will become more critical. On the one hand, the system design and operation process of the working group should be further optimized. At the institutional level, the legal status, responsibilities and powers, and supervision and accountability mechanisms of the working group should be clarified to ensure that its operation is legal, standardized and transparent; in terms of operation process, information technology should be used to optimize resource allocation, information sharing, and communication and collaboration processes to improve work efficiency and accuracy. For example, a resource intelligent allocation system based on big data analysis can be established to achieve accurate allocation and efficient use of resources; an integrated information communication platform can be built to break down information silos between departments and promote real-time communication and collaborative work.

On the other hand, we need to strengthen the capacity building and experience promotion of the working group. In terms of capacity building, we should focus on improving the comprehensive quality of the members of the working group, including professional skills, communication and collaboration skills, innovation ability and emergency response ability, and build a high-quality and professional working team through regular training, practical training and experience exchange. In terms of experience promotion, we should systematically

summarize the practical experience of successful cases, form standardized operation modes and case libraries, and provide reference examples and guidance for working groups in other regions or projects. At the same time, we encourage working groups of different regions and types to carry out exchanges and cooperation, jointly explore innovative working methods and mechanisms, promote the continuous development and improvement of working groups in the construction of large-scale projects, and provide strong support for the modernization of grassroots governance systems and governance capabilities.

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